

ASSESSMENT OF AWARENESS OF GERIATRIC DENTAL CARE AMONG POSTGRADUATES AND PRACTITIONERS OF CHHATTISGARH STATE

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION

The overall health and wellness of older adults are one of the factors related to their oral health. For developing attitudes towards older people is also a key component in the development of professional behaviours and practical patterns of postgraduate students and practitioners. There is a need for understanding and addressing the oral health of geriatric population and integrate them with overall health care aspects.

AIM & OBJECTIVES

To assess and compare the awareness of Geriatric Dental Care among Postgraduates and Practitioners of Chhattisgarh State and compare variations among Postgraduates and Practitioners.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional questionnaire-based survey was undertaken among the First to Final MDS students of Dental colleges and Practitioners of Chhattisgarh State.

RESULT

48% of students said they pay more attention and have more sympathy to the elderly patients than young'. Among the participants, 86% said they had previous experience on geriatric dental care.

CONCLUSION

Postgraduates and Practitioners showed their awareness towards geriatric dental care. Postgraduates showed more awareness towards geriatric dental care. They also suggested to have better treatment facilities for treatment and care of geriatric patient.

KEYWORDS

Geriatric, Dental care, Postgraduates, Practitioners, Chhattisgarh

INTRODUCTION

Geriatric dentistry is a science which deals with the diagnosis, management, and prevention of all types of oral diseases in the elderly population. It focuses on delivery of dental care to the older population and addresses age-related dental ailments.¹ Growing geriatric population poses significant healthcare system challenges, including deteriorating oral health².

Oral health constitutes a major component of an individual's overall health². Oral health, according to Dolan, is described as "a comfortable and effective dentition that permits individuals to maintain their intended social position". Oral health is so vital that it can interfere with a person's ability to work and concentrate on their everyday activities.³

The rapid growing of the population comes with a number of difficulties in terms of general and oral health. A continuing progress in the medical field has raised the longevity of life.⁴ Oral diseases qualify as major public health problems owing to their high prevalence and incidence in all regions of the world, and as for all diseases, the greatest burden of oral diseases is under privileged and socially marginalized populations.⁵

Older adults have a more complex presentation of diseases and illnesses than any other population due to higher incidences of numerous comorbidities and functional impairments.⁶ Improvement in the health status of the population has resulted in an increase in the number of elderly surviving to an advanced age.⁷ An ageing population is one of the most important aspects of the 21st century world-wide and will be one of the major challenges for the next millennium.⁸

AIM

To assess the awareness of Geriatric Dental Care among Postgraduates and Practitioners of Chhattisgarh State.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the awareness of Geriatric Dental Care among Postgraduates and Practitioners of Chhattisgarh State.
2. To compare variations of awareness of Geriatric Dental Care among Postgraduates and Practitioners.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

The study was administered out on Postgraduate dental students from first to final MDS students studying in dental colleges and Practitioners of Chhattisgarh state.

Study design

A cross-sectional based study was designed. A questionnaire was distributed among first to final MDS students and Practitioners.

Study population

There was total 100 participants from Chhattisgarh state. There were about 60 female participants and 40 male participants.

Study procedure

The validated questionnaire consisted of total 25 questions. The Inclusion criterion was all the willing participants of first to final MDS and practitioners of Chhattisgarh state. The unwilling participants was the exclusion criteria. The questionnaire was distributed in form of google forms.

RESULTS

The present study was carried out among the dental postgraduates and practitioners of Chhattisgarh state. There were about 100 participants; out of which 60 female and 40 male participants.

48.0% of participants agreed that they pay more attention and have more sympathy to the elderly patients than young. 55.0% of agreed that they understand the physical and mental limitations of elderly people. 56.0% of participants agreed that as people get old, they become less organized and more confused. 49.0% of participants said that providing care to old people takes more time in comparison to the younger patients. 41.0% of participants said providing care for the old people is the society responsibility. 46.0% agreed that elderly people appreciate the health service more than the young ones. 35.0% agree that management of chronically ill older patients is disappointing. 24% said that if they have a choice, they would prefer to provide care to the young patients than old ones. 50.0% said that taking medical and dental history from an older patient is difficult and challenging and 48.0% of participants agreed that older people have problems in paying their health care costs. Detailed description of all questions are given in Table 2.

Self-reported ability of the dentists towards the provision of dental care to the elderly patients, Important barriers for provision of dental care to elderly patients, Independent variables by postgraduates and practitioners and among the common systemic diseases found in the patients of the participants is elaborated in Table 3, 4, 5A and 5B respectively. The variations of attitude among postgraduates and practitioners are elaborated in table 6, 7, 8, 9A and 9B respectively.

Table 2. Overall distribution of the responses to the questions under ‘Attitude of the postgraduates and practitioners towards providing dental care to the elderly patients’

Questions		Agree	Completely Agree	Completely Disagree	Disagree	Don't Know	Total
I pay more attention and have more sympathy to the elderly patients than young	N	48	32	2	13	5	100
	%	48.0%	32.0%	2.0%	13.0%	5.0%	100%
I do understand the physical and mental limitations of elderly people	N	55	41	0	1	3	100
	%	55.0%	41.0%	0.0%	1.0%	3.0%	100%
As people get old, they become less organized and more confused	N	56	24	0	15	5	100
	%	56.0%	24.0%	0.0%	15.0%	5.0%	100%
Providing care to old people takes more time in comparison to the younger patients	N	49	32	1	14	4	100
	%	49.0%	32.0%	1.0%	14.0%	4.0%	100%
Providing care for the old people is the society responsibility	N	41	55	0	3	1	100
	%	41.0%	55.0%	0.0%	3.0%	1.0%	100%
Elderly people appreciate the health service more than the young ones	N	46	30	2	13	9	100
	%	46.0%	30.0%	2.0%	13.0%	9.0%	100%
Management of chronically ill older patients is disappointing	N	35	6	31	24	4	100
	%	35.0%	6.0%	31.0%	24.0%	4.0%	100%
If I have a choice, I would prefer to provide care to the young patients than old ones	N	24	2	22	41	11	100
	%	24.0%	2.0%	22.0%	41.0%	11.0%	100%
Taking medical and dental history from an older patient is difficult and challenging	N	50	9	2	34	5	100
	%	50.0%	9.0%	2.0%	34.0%	5.0%	100%
Older people have problems in paying their health care costs	N	48	11	2	24	15	100
	%	48.0%	11.0%	2.0%	24.0%	15.0%	100%

Table 3. Overall distribution of the responses to the questions under ‘Self-reported ability of the dentists towards the provision of dental care to the elderly patients’

Questions		Agree	Completely Agree	Completely Disagree	Disagree	Don't Know	Total
I make dental treatment plan according to the needs and preferences of the old patients	N	60	35	1	2	2	100
	%	60.0%	35.0%	1.0%	2.0%	2.0%	100%
I am able to communicate appropriately with the old patients	N	58	31	0	3	8	100
	%	58.0%	31.0%	0.0%	3.0%	8.0%	100%
I am able to plan preventive	N	58	28	1	4	9	100

care for the old patients	%	58.0%	28.0%	1.0%	4.0%	9.0%	100%
I am able to manage the medical emergencies of the old patients	N	54	22	0	8	16	100
	%	54.0%	22.0%	0.0%	8.0%	16.0%	100%
I am able to express the sense of empathy and needs of old people	N	55	41	0	0	4	100
	%	55.0%	41.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.0%	100%

Table 4. Overall distribution of the responses to the questions under ‘Important barriers for provision of dental care to elderly patients’

Questions		Agree	Completely Agree	Completely Disagree	Disagree	Don't Know	Total
Follow up of elderly patients	N	47	48	0	1	4	100
	%	47.0%	48.0%	0.0%	1.0%	4.0%	100%
Treating old patients are time consuming	N	55	17	1	15	12	100
	%	55.0%	17.0%	1.0%	15.0%	12.0%	100%
Inadequate communication skills	N	38	6	2	36	18	100
	%	38.0%	6.0%	2.0%	36.0%	18.0%	100%
Lack of appropriate treatment facilities	N	63	11	2	15	9	100
	%	63.0%	11.0%	2.0%	15.0%	9.0%	100%

Table 5A. Overall distribution of the responses to the questions under ‘Independent variables by postgraduates and practitioners’

Questions		No	Yes	Total
Do you have previous experience on geriatric dental care?	N	14	86	100
	%	14.0%	86.0%	100%
Should geriatric dental care be a part of teaching curriculum as training?	N	4	96	100
	%	4.0%	96.0%	100%
Do you think training on geriatric dental care is required?	N	5	95	100
	%	5.0%	95.0%	100%
Do you think there is lack of appropriate treatment facilities for geriatric patients?	N	22	78	100
	%	22.0%	78.0%	100%
Have you treated any geriatric patients?	N	10	90	100
	%	10.0%	90.0%	100%

Table 5B. Overall distribution of the responses to the question ‘If yes, which common systemic diseases was/were found in your patients?’

Common systemic diseases		Total
Diabetes Mellitus	N	50
	%	50.0%
Hypertension	N	36
	%	36.0%
Cardiovascular diseases	N	6
	%	6.0%
Respiratory disease	N	2
	%	2.0%
Thyroid diseases	N	3
	%	3.0%
Neurological disease	N	6
	%	6.0%
Bone diseases	N	3
	%	3.0%

Table 6. Comparison of the responses to the questions under ‘Attitude of the postgraduates and practitioners towards providing dental care to the elderly patients’ between the postgraduates and practitioners

Questions		Agree	Completely Agree	Completely Disagree	Disagree	Don't Know	Total	P value		
I pay more attention and have more sympathy to the elderly patients than young	Postgraduates	N	34	14	2	4	3	57	0.024*	
		%	59.6%	24.6%	3.5%	7.0%	5.3%			100%
	Practitioners	N	14	18	0	9	2			43
		%	32.6%	41.9%	0.0%	20.9%	4.7%			
I do understand the physical and mental limitations of elderly people	Postgraduates	N	32	23	0	1	1	57	0.686	
		%	56.1%	40.4%	0.0%	1.8%	1.8%			100%
	Practitioners	N	23	18	0	0	2			43
		%	53.5%	41.9%	0.0%	0.0%	4.7%			
As people get old, they become less organized and	Postgraduates	N	36	13	0	6	2	57	0.302	
		%	63.2%	22.8%	0.0%	10.5%	3.5%			100%
	Practitioners	N	20	11	0	9	3			43
		%	46.5%	25.6%	0.0%	20.9%	7.0%			

more confused									
Providing care to old people takes more time in comparison to the younger patients	Postgraduates	N	33	15	1	7	1	57	0.186
		%	57.9%	26.3%	1.8%	12.3%	1.8%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	16	17	0	7	3	43	
		%	37.2%	39.5%	0.0%	16.3%	7.0%	100%	
Providing care for the old people is the society responsibility	Postgraduates	N	27	28	0	1	1	57	0.310
		%	47.4%	49.1%	0.0%	1.8%	1.8%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	14	27	0	2	0	43	
		%	32.6%	62.8%	0.0%	4.7%	0.0%	100%	
Elderly people appreciate the health service more than the young ones	Postgraduates	N	33	13	0	5	6	57	0.025*
		%	57.9%	22.8%	0.0%	8.8%	10.5%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	13	17	2	8	3	43	
		%	30.2%	39.5%	4.7%	18.6%	7.0%	100%	
Management of chronically ill older patients is disappointing	Postgraduates	N	19	2	20	14	2	57	0.683
		%	33.3%	3.5%	35.1%	24.6%	3.5%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	16	4	11	10	2	43	
		%	37.2%	9.3%	25.6%	23.3%	4.7%	100%	
If I have a choice, I would prefer to provide care to the young patients than old ones	Postgraduates	N	17	1	14	17	8	57	0.114
		%	29.8%	1.8%	24.6%	29.8%	14.0%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	7	1	8	24	3	43	
		%	16.3%	2.3%	18.6%	55.8%	7.0%	100%	
Taking medical and dental history from an older patient is difficult and challenging	Postgraduates	N	33	2	1	18	3	57	0.172
		%	57.9%	3.5%	1.8%	31.6%	5.3%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	17	7	1	16	2	43	
		%	39.5%	16.3%	2.3%	37.2%	4.7%	100%	
Older people have problems in paying their health care costs	Postgraduates	N	31	4	1	15	6	57	0.273
		%	54.4%	7.0%	1.8%	26.3%	10.5%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	17	7	1	9	9	43	
		%	39.5%	16.3%	2.3%	20.9%	20.9%	100%	

Table 7. Comparison of the responses to the questions under ‘Self-reported ability of the dentists towards the provision of dental care to the elderly patients’ between the postgraduates and practitioners

Questions			Agree	Completely Agree	Completely Disagree	Disagree	Don't Know	Total	P value
I make dental treatment plan according to the needs and preferences of the old patients	Postgraduates	N	36	19	0	0	2	57	0.214
		%	63.2%	33.3%	0.0%	0.0%	3.5%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	24	16	1	2	0	43	
		%	55.8%	37.2%	2.3%	4.7%	0.0%	100%	
I am able to communicate appropriately with the old patients	Postgraduates	N	33	16	0	1	7	57	0.252
		%	57.9%	28.1%	0.0%	1.8%	12.3%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	25	15	0	2	1	43	
		%	58.1%	34.9%	0.0%	4.7%	2.3%	100%	
I am able to plan preventive care for the old patients	Postgraduates	N	33	15	0	2	7	57	0.534
		%	57.9%	26.3%	0.0%	3.5%	12.3%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	25	13	1	2	2	43	
		%	58.1%	30.2%	2.3%	4.7%	4.7%	100%	
I am able to manage the medical emergencies of the old patients	Postgraduates	N	34	12	0	2	9	57	0.242
		%	59.6%	21.1%	0.0%	3.5%	15.8%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	20	10	0	6	7	43	
		%	46.5%	23.3%	0.0%	14.0%	16.3%	100%	
I am able to express the sense of empathy and needs of old people	Postgraduates	N	31	23	0	0	3	57	0.759
		%	54.4%	40.4%	0.0%	0.0%	5.3%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	24	18	0	0	1	43	
		%	55.8%	41.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.3%	100%	

Table 8. Comparison of the responses to the questions under ‘Important barriers for provision of dental care to elderly patients’ between the postgraduates and practitioners

Questions			Agree	Completely Agree	Completely Disagree	Disagree	Don't Know	Total	P value
Follow up of elderly patients	Postgraduates	N	28	25	0	1	3	57	0.597
		%	49.1%	43.9%	0.0%	1.8%	5.3%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	19	23	0	0	1	43	
		%	44.2%	53.5%	0.0%	0.0%	2.3%	100%	

		%	44.2%	53.5%	0.0%	0.0%	2.3%	100%	
Treating old patients are time consuming	Postgraduates	N	34	6	1	8	8	57	0.279
		%	59.6%	10.5%	1.8%	14.0%	14.0%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	21	11	0	7	4	43	
		%	48.8%	25.6%	0.0%	16.3%	9.3%	100%	
Inadequate communication skills	Postgraduates	N	21	4	2	20	10	57	0.767
		%	36.8%	7.0%	3.5%	35.1%	17.5%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	17	2	0	16	8	43	
		%	39.5%	4.7%	0.0%	37.2%	18.6%	100%	
Lack of appropriate treatment facilities	Postgraduates	N	35	6	2	9	5	57	0.799
		%	61.4%	10.5%	3.5%	15.8%	8.8%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	28	5	0	6	4	43	
		%	65.1%	11.6%	0.0%	14.0%	9.3%	100%	

Table 9A. Comparison of the responses to the questions under ‘Independent variables by postgraduates and practitioners’ between the postgraduates and practitioners

Questions			No	Yes	Total	P value
Do you have previous experience on geriatric dental care?	Postgraduates	N	6	51	57	0.249
		%	10.5%	89.5%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	8	35	43	
		%	18.6%	81.4%	100%	
Should geriatric dental care be a part of teaching curriculum as training?	Postgraduates	N	3	54	57	0.458
		%	5.3%	94.7%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	1	42	43	
		%	2.3%	97.7%	100%	
Do you think training on geriatric dental care is required?	Postgraduates	N	3	54	57	0.889
		%	5.3%	94.7%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	2	41	43	
		%	4.7%	95.3%	100%	
Do you think there is lack of appropriate treatment facilities for geriatric patients?	Postgraduates	N	10	47	57	0.216
		%	17.5%	82.5%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	12	31	43	
		%	27.9%	72.1%	100%	
Have you treated any geriatric patients?	Postgraduates	N	5	52	57	0.637
		%	8.8%	91.2%	100%	
	Practitioners	N	5	38	43	
		%	11.6%	88.4%	100%	

Table 9B. Comparison of the responses to the question ‘If yes, which common systemic diseases was/were found in your patients?’ between the postgraduates and practitioners

Common systemic diseases			Total
Diabetes Mellitus	Postgraduates	N	27
		%	47.4%
	Practitioners	N	23
		%	53.5%
Hypertension	Postgraduates	N	18
		%	31.6%
	Practitioners	N	18
		%	41.9%
Cardiovascular diseases	Postgraduates	N	2
		%	3.5%
	Practitioners	N	4
		%	9.3%
Respiratory disease	Postgraduates	N	1
		%	1.8%
	Practitioners	N	1
		%	2.3%
Thyroid diseases	Postgraduates	N	1
		%	1.8%
	Practitioners	N	2
		%	4.7%
Neurological disease	Postgraduates	N	3
		%	5.3%
	Practitioners	N	3
		%	7.0%
Bone diseases	Postgraduates	N	0
		%	0.0%
	Practitioners	N	3
		%	7.0%

DISCUSSION

India is the second most populous country of the world and 8% of the total population of India constitutes geriatric population. This percentage is expected to rise to approx. 10 - 12% of entire population. The population growth rate of 1.58%, it is predicted that India has > 1.53 billion population at the end of 2030. Around 100 million elderly are in India at present,

and it is expected that number will increase to 323 million, by 2050, constituting 20% of the total world's population.⁹

Abhishek Purohit et al⁹ found that 74% of participants said they have previous experience on geriatric dental care, 97% of participants said that geriatric dental care should be a part of teaching curriculum as training and 90% of participants thought that training on geriatric dental care is required whereas in our study we found that 86.0% have previous experience on geriatric dental care, 96.0% of participants agreed to the same and 95.0% participants said the same.

Anton Rahardjo et al¹⁰, he found that 21.8% of participants choice to see younger patients rather than elderly ones and 74.5% of participants agreed that as people grow older, they become less organized and more confused in our study we found that 48% of participants s choice to see younger patients rather than elderly ones and 56% agreed that as people grow older, they become less organized and more confused.

Anton Rahardjo et al¹⁰, he found that 52.7% of participants agreed that elderly patients tend to be more appreciative of the medical care than younger patients and in this study 46% of participants agreed to the same.

Divyalakshmi G et al¹¹ she found that 60% of participants said it is very important to have adequate treatment facilities for geriatric care, whereas Abhishek Purohit et al⁹ found that 29% of participants said the same and in our study we found that 78.0% of participants agreed to this.

LIMITATIONS

The questionnaire was self-reported therefore answers given by the participants could be biased. The study result cannot be generalized for the Indian population because, the survey was limited to dental students and Practitioners of Chhattisgarh state only. The survey may be extended by conducting it in large scale in different dental colleges of India to expand the sample size to get more precise results which can be generalized.

CONCLUSION

The study participants showed their awareness towards geriatric dental care. Among participants Postgraduates showed more awareness towards geriatric dental care. They also suggested to have better treatment facilities for treatment and care of geriatric patients. But at the same time, it's necessary to conduct training and education programs to implement best geriatric dental care in institute's and to deliver perfect rehabilitation with blending of skills.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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